

Synthesis and Structural Studies of Salicylaldazine Complexes of Oxovanadium(IV), Manganese(II), Iron(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Zinc(II)

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Neutral complexes of the type $M(SA).nH_2O$, where $M = VO^{IV}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}$ or Zn^{II} ; SA = dianion of salicylaldazine; $n = 1$ for VO^{IV} and Zn^{II} , and 2 for other metal ions, have been prepared. The complexes are non-electrolytes as is evident from low values of their molar conductance ($10-15 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$) in DMF solutions. The magnetic moment values and electronic spectral data suggest that the $Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}$ and Ni^{II} complexes are outer-orbital octahedral while Cu^{II} complex is distorted octahedral. Infrared spectral studies indicate that SA^{2-} behaves as a tetradentate ligand bonding through the two azomethine nitrogens and both the phenolic oxygens. TGA and ir studies show that the water molecule(s) are coordinated in all the complexes except the Zn^{II} complex where it is present in the lattice. X-ray powder diffraction studies of $Cu(SA).2H_2O$ and $Zn(SA).H_2O$ suggest that they are not isomorphous and belong to hexagonal and orthorhombic crystal systems, respectively

THE 3d metal(II) complexes of salicylaldazine *o*-HO-C₆H₄CH=N-N=CHC₆H₄OH-*o*-(H₂SA)²⁻ have been prepared but no definite conclusions have been drawn about the mode of bonding of the ligand and the stereochemistry of the complexes. In view of the inadequacy of the previous work and our continuing interest in transition metal complexes of salicylaldimines^{4,5}, the research work on the title complexes was undertaken and the results of these investigations are reported in the present paper.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR quality. Salicylaldazine (H₂SA) was prepared by the literature procedure⁶. Purity of the ligand was checked from its m.p. 213° (lit⁶. 213-14°) (Found: N₂H₄, 13.50. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₂O₂N₂: N₂H₄, 13.33%).

Preparation and analysis of complexes: VO(SA).H₂O was prepared by adding hydrazine hydrate to a methanolic solution of bis(salicylaldehydato)-aquoovanadium(IV)⁷ in 1:1 molar ratio and warming the reaction mixture for ~15 min. The complex thus precipitated was filtered, washed with methanol and finally with CHCl₃, and dried at room temperature. The other M(SA).nH₂O complexes, where M=Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}, were prepared by reacting aqueous solutions of the respective metal chloride with H₂SA dissolved in minimum quantity of aqueous NaOH in 1:1 molar ratio. Fe(SA).2H₂O was prepared similarly employing methanolic solutions

and carrying out the reaction under hydrogen atmosphere. The complexes precipitated immediately and were filtered, washed with very dilute acetic acid and finally with chloroform, and dried *in vacuo*.

The complexes were analysed for metal, nitrogen, hydrazine and water content. Experimental details pertaining to the analyses, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, electronic and ir spectral measurements were the same as described in our earlier paper⁴. The results are given in Tables 1 and 2. The X-ray powder photograph for Cu(SA).2H₂O and Zn(SA).H₂O were obtained on a Philips X-ray generator using nickel filtered CuK_α radiation and a Debye-Scherrer camera.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) show that H₂SA yields neutral complexes of the general formula M(SA).nH₂O, where $n = 1$ for Zn^{II} and VO^{IV}, and 2 for other metal ions. The complexes do not melt but decompose in the temperature range 200-300°. The complete loss of water molecule(s) at ~110° in the case of Zn^{II} complex and at relatively higher temperatures (160-170°) in the case of other complexes showed that the water molecule(s) are lattice-held in the former and coordinated in the latter complexes⁸. These findings about the nature of water molecules in the hydrated complexes is supported by the presence of a band in 755-800 cm⁻¹ region, characteristic of coordinated water in complexes of all metal ions except that of Zn^{II}

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC MOMENT AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/Calcd.)			Weight loss % ^a Found/ (Calcd)	μ_{eff} ^b B.M.	Molar conduc- tance in DMF $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		Metal	N	N ₂ H ₄			
VO(SA).H ₂ O	Brown	15.10 (15.77)	8.71 (8.67)	—	5.40 (5.57)	1.70	11.5
Mn(SA).2H ₂ O	Orange yellow	16.95 (16.70)	8.41 (8.51)	9.60 (9.73)	10.71 (10.94)	6.04	10.0
Fe(SA).2H ₂ O	Dark brown	17.02 (16.93)	8.64 (8.49)	9.75 (9.70)	10.54 (10.91)	5.00	11.5
Co(SA).2H ₂ O	Dark pink	17.53 (17.70)	8.51 (8.41)	10.10 (9.61)	10.53 (10.81)	4.97	14.0
Co(SA)	Brownish red	20.10 (19.84)	9.46 (9.43)	—	—	4.83	—
Ni(SA).2H ₂ O	Yellow	17.10 (17.64)	8.70 (8.42)	9.34 (9.62)	10.56 (10.82)	3.24	13.6
Ni(SA)	Yellowish green	19.40 (19.78)	9.02 (9.44)	—	—	2.95	—
Cu(SA).2H ₂ O	Light brown	19.46 (18.82)	8.24 (8.30)	—	10.89 (10.67)	1.87	15.0
Cu(SA)	Brown	21.21 (21.08)	9.58 (9.29)	—	—	1.86	—
Zn(SA).H ₂ O	Yellow	20.80 (20.34)	8.60 (8.71)	9.93 (9.96)	5.40 (5.60)	Diamag.	12.8

^aTemp. 110° for Zn²⁺ complex and 160–170° for other complexes. ^bAt 298 k.

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA AND LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	λ_{max} cm ⁻¹	Assignments	10 Dq cm ⁻¹	B' cm ⁻¹	β	β^0	LFSE kJmol ⁻¹
VO(SA).H ₂ O	12 900, 15 380	$d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{yz}, d_{xz}; d_{x^2-y^2}$	15 380	—	—	—	73.4
Fe(SA).2H ₂ O	16 600	${}^6T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^6E_g$ (D)	16 600	—	—	—	79.2
Co(SA).2H ₂ O	10 800	${}^4T_{1g}$ (F) \rightarrow ${}^4T_{2g}$ (F)	—	—	—	—	—
Co(SA)	9 525, 21 050	${}^4T_{1g}$ (F) \rightarrow ${}^4T_{2g}$ (F), ${}^4T_{1g}$ (P)	10 810	854	0.878	12.20	103.1
Ni(SA).2H ₂ O	10 530, 17 600	${}^3A_{2g}$ (F) \rightarrow ${}^3T_{2g}$ (F), ${}^3T_{1g}$ (F)	10 530	896	0.850	15.10	150.7
Ni(SA)	10 700	${}^3A_{2g}$ (F) \rightarrow ${}^3T_{2g}$ (F)	10 700	—	—	—	153.0
Cu(SA).2H ₂ O	14 300	${}^2E_g \rightarrow T_{2g}$	14 300	—	—	—	102.3
Cu(SA)	15 400	${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$	15 400	—	—	—	110.2

(Ref. 9). The complexes are insoluble in water and in organic solvents, such as ethanol, methanol, THF and acetone, and slightly soluble in DMF and DMSO. The molar conductance values (10–15 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) of the complexes in DMF show their non-ionic nature¹⁰.

Magnetic moment: The μ_{eff} values (Table 1) indicate that the hydrated as well as anhydrous complexes of Fe²⁺, Co²⁺ and Ni²⁺ are spin-free and have octahedral geometry¹¹. The magnetic moment of Mn²⁺ complex corresponds to five unpaired electrons while μ_{eff} values of Cu²⁺ and VO²⁺ complexes correspond to one unpaired electron indicating spin-free nature of the former complex but giving no specific information about the stereochemistry of the latter.

Electronic spectra: The uv spectra of H₂SA in nujol show three bands at 27 400, 34 500 and 45 450 cm^{-1} while the spectra of the complexes in the 20 000–50 000 cm^{-1} region also show three bands at 23 250–23 800, 33 000 and 40 000–44 400 cm^{-1} . The 27 400 cm^{-1} band of the ligand corresponding to the 30 300 cm^{-1} band of free salicylaldehyde¹² is considerably red-shifted (23 250–23 800

cm^{-1}) in the complexes due to the formation of salicylaldehydato ion and its subsequent participation in chelate ring formation around the metal ion¹³ (1). The number and position of the d-d transition bands and assignments thereof (Table 2) suggest the octahedral geometry for the hydrated as well as anhydrous complexes of VO²⁺, Fe²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Cu²⁺ (Refs. 14–18). The broadness of the d-d transition band and ν_{OH} / ν_{NH} ratio of 1.36–1.44 (Ref. 19) in Cu²⁺ complexes indicate that they are tetragonally distorted. The visible spectrum of Mn²⁺ complex yields no d-d transition bands because these bands appear to have submerged into the strong intra-molecular transitions of the salicylaldehydato ion.

The D_q values of the complexes suggest that SA lies between water and ammonia in the spectrochemical series while β^0 values indicate 12.2–15.1% covalency in the metal-ligand bond.

Infrared spectra: The infrared spectra of the ligand in nujol show a broad band at 3 450 cm^{-1} assigned to ν_{OH} which is shifted to 3 700 cm^{-1} in the chloroform solution, indicating the presence of hydrogen bonding in the ligand in the solid state.

The spectra of the hydrated complexes show a broad band in 3 400-3 470 cm^{-1} region which may be attributed to ν_{OH} of the water molecules present in these complexes. A single $\nu_{C=N}$ band observed at 1 625 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the ligand suffered a negative shift of 10-25 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes, indicating coordination through both the symmetrical azomethine nitrogen atoms. Satapathy and Sahoo³ reported two $\nu_{C=N}$ bands at 1 613 and 1 595 cm^{-1} in the case of Fe^{2+} complex but we observed only one band at 1 600 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of $\text{Fe}(\text{SA})\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, which suggests that both the C=N groups of the ligand are involved in coordination in the above complex just as in other complexes. The coordination through both the azomethine nitrogens is further supported by a positive shift of 55-100 cm^{-1} in N-N stretching frequency in the spectra of the complexes²⁰. A positive shift of 13-50 cm^{-1} in $\nu_{C=O}$ band in the complexes as compared to the ligand (1 272 cm^{-1}) and appearance of a new band due to $\nu_{asym}(\text{C-O})$ in the region 1 530-1 545 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the hydrated complexes and around 1 550 cm^{-1} in the anhydrous complexes indicate the presence of C-O-M moiety in these complexes and also the unidentate nature of the C-O group in former complexes and its bridging bidentate nature in the latter^{21,22}. The 960 cm^{-1} band appearing in the oxovanadium(IV) complex is assigned to $\nu_{\nu-O}$ ²³ while the non-ligand bands appearing in this and other complexes in the regions 250-465 and 325-390 cm^{-1} are tentatively assigned to ν_{M-O} ^{24,25} and $\nu_{M\leftarrow N}$ ^{26,27} modes, respectively.

X-Ray powder diffraction: The indexing of the X-ray diffraction lines were done by Hess-Lipson's method²⁸ and it was found that most of the prominent diffraction lines could be satisfactorily indexed for hexagonal and orthorhombic symmetries for $\text{Cu}(\text{SA})\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Zn}(\text{SA})\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, respectively. The lattice parameters calculated for the above symmetries are: $a=10.267\text{\AA}$, $C=16.05\text{\AA}$, $V=732\text{\AA}^3$ for $\text{Cu}(\text{SA})\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $a=7.492\text{\AA}$, $b=12.58\text{\AA}$, $c=16.08$ and $V=1515\text{\AA}^3$ for $\text{Zn}(\text{SA})\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The powder X-ray diffraction photograph of these complexes show that they are not isomorphous.

M(SA) \cdot 2H₂O
M = Fe, Co, Ni, Cu
1

Based on the composition and physicochemical studies, the following structure (1) could be proposed for the $\text{M}(\text{SA})\cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complexes.

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